

VISCOSITY AND DENSITY OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF MERCURIC CHLORIDE AT 35°.

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Viscosity and density of aqueous solutions of mercuric chloride have been measured at 35° from 0.001534 to 0.2652 g. mole/litre (almost saturated solution) with a viscometer in which neither kinetic correction nor surface tension correction was necessary. The density increases linearly with concentration throughout the entire range and can be represented by the equation $\rho = 0.9941 + 0.228 c$. Viscosity too increases linearly with concentration for dilute solutions ($\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.125c$), but at a concentration near about $M/10$ and above the viscosity begins to increase more rapidly. This linear variation of viscosity with concentration in dilute solutions is taken as a proof of the behaviour of mercuric chloride as almost a non-electrolyte in aqueous solutions.

The viscosity of dilute solutions of non-electrolytes was measured by one of the authors (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 499) who showed that in dilute solutions, viscosity increases linearly with concentration. Mercuric chloride behaves as a very weak electrolyte in both conductivity and electromotive force measurements and so, it was expected to behave more or less as a non-electrolyte in viscosity measurements. The experiments were undertaken to test the validity of this expectation.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The thermostat used was of the same type as that described in the paper referred to above. The temperature was kept at $35^\circ \pm .005$. Viscosity was measured with the same kind of viscometer, except that the mark below the bulb on the capillary side was made just above the capillary tube at a place where the bore was several times greater than the bore of the capillary. The viscometer was fixed in a frame, so that a number of adjustments described in the previous paper were rendered unnecessary. For observing the level of the liquid in the wider limb, a telescope giving a linear magnification of three at a distance of two feet was used. Five readings for time were taken in case of every solution and the mean was used in calculating viscosity. The bore of the capillary tube in the viscometer used was about 0.28 mm. and its length about 10 cm. The volume of the bulb above the capillary tube was about 5 c.c. and the time of transpiration about 30 minutes.

Density measurements were made with a pycnometer of about 20 c. c. capacity, provided with stoppers and ending in vertical capillary limbs of about 1 mm. bore (instead of the usual type with horizontal limbs) so that the whole of the liquid could be kept well under the surface of water in the thermostat. After the liquid in the pycnometer had attained the temperature of the bath, the level was adjusted with a fine platinum syringe to marks made near about the middle of each capillary limb. Two determinations were made with the pycnometer in each case and the results never differed by more than 1 mg. Double distilled water was used in making all the solutions.

No surface tension correction was necessary on account of the design of the viscometer. No kinetic correction was necessary, as found by the method suggested by Barr (*A Monograph of Viscometry*, Oxford, 1931, p. 127).

In the following table, the concentrations of solutions of mercuric chloride, their density and viscosity are given. By concentration is meant g. moles/litre and by viscosity the relative viscosity, *i.e.*, viscosity of solution/viscosity of water at the same temperature (35°).

TABLE I.

Conc. $\times 10^5$.	Density.	Viscosity.	Conc. $\times 10^5$.	Density.	Viscosity.
0	0.9941	1.0000	2950.0	1.0008	1.0037
153.4	0.9944	0.9998	3699.0	1.0023	1.0045
302.0	0.9949	1.0004	4420.0	1.0039	1.0054
452.7	0.9951	1.0003	5152.0	1.0054	1.0064
593.8	0.9955	1.0004	5900.0	1.0072	1.0074
749.2	0.9958	1.0010	6630.0	1.0089	1.0090
882.5	0.9961	1.0009	7367.0	1.0105	1.0095
1033.0	0.9963	1.0009	8840.0	1.0137	1.0113
1182.0	0.9969	1.0017	10314.0	1.0169	1.0138
1329.0	0.9970	1.0013	11787.0	1.0201	1.0157
1526.0	0.9976	1.0023	14733.0	1.0268	1.0203
1768.0	0.9980	1.0021	17679.0	1.0333	1.0245
2063.0	0.9987	1.0029	20626.0	1.0407	1.0292
2357.0	0.9994	1.0034	23557.0	1.0472	1.0342
2652.0	1.0000	1.0033	26520.0	1.0538	1.0378

The maximum possible error in the values of viscosity (η/η_0), as found by assuming a maximum error of 0.2 second in the time of transpiration and 0.001 g. in weights comes out to be 0.0003, but the actual error in most cases should be much less.

In Fig. 1, the viscosity of the solutions is plotted against concentration.

FIG. 1.

In the following figure, density of all the solutions is plotted against concentration.

FIG. 2.

DISCUSSION.

An examination of the results given in the table as well as those plotted in Fig. 1 shows that the variation of viscosity is so small that at low concentrations, the difference between the viscosity of two successive solutions is within the limits of the possible experimental error (0.0003).

To test whether mercuric chloride behaves as an electrolyte or non-electrolyte, η/η_0 was plotted against c . A straight line passing through the origin was obtained by the method of least squares up to a concentration of 0.08840 g. mole per litre. The viscosity of seventeen out of twenty-three solutions, thus plotted, could be represented by the equation, $\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + 0.125c$, within the possible experimental error. In four cases, the difference between the observed and the calculated results was 0.0004, in one case 0.0005 and in another 0.0007. This very fact would be enough to show that mercuric chloride behaves as a non-electrolyte, but in order to make sure, the A and B values of Jones and Dole equation (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, **51**, 2950; Falkenhagen and Vernon, *Phil. Mag.*, 1932, **14**, 537).

$$\eta/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{c} + Bc$$

were found by plotting $\eta/\eta_0 - 1/\sqrt{c}$ against $\sqrt{c}$. The intercept on the ordinate gives A and the slope of the line gives B . It is found that a very small negative value can be given to A . No positive value is possible. The results are equally well represented if $A=0$, which means that mercuric chloride is a non-electrolyte. Moreover, the negative value does not seem to have any significance.

Density (ρ) of the solutions varies linearly with concentration from the lowest to highest concentrations and can be represented to an accuracy of 0.1% by the equation $\rho = 0.9941 + 0.228c$.

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